

PHENOLOGICAL STUDY OF DIFFERENT SPECIES OF TREES AT DALPUR, HIMMATNAGAR DISTRICT, NORTH GUJARAT, INDIA.

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ABSTRACT:

The study of phenology examines the link between stages of the same or different events, the timing of recurrent biological processes and the abiotic and biotic forces that affect those timings. In dalpur, which is situated in the Himmatnagar district in the northern part of Gujarat state, the current study was document the phonological study of different tree species. This study includes the tree lifecycle, which includes leaf fall, vegetative growth, fruiting, flowering, new foliage during 2021 to 2024. Phenological phases of different species of tree showed that the peak of leaf fall occurred during the cool dry period in January (66%), fruited during the start of the warm dry period in May (56%), and flowered during the warm dry period in March through April (73% and 73%, respectively).

KEYWORDS: Phenology, Shedding, Flowering, Fruiting, Himmatnagar, Gujarat.

INTRODUCTION:

Phenology is the study of how weather patterns in seasons and years relate to the growth of buds, leaf flushing, anthesis, fruiting, and leaf fall. Researchers can better understand how biotic and abiotic variables affect the start of disease and different events known as phenophases by understanding the phenological patterns in plants. The study of phenology investigates the relationship between seasons of years with specific meteorological conditions and the growth of buds, flushing of leaves, anthesis, fruiting, and leaf fall. The life cycles of most species are repeated, but the most studied is definitely plant phenology. Plant phenology studies processes that are closely related to ecosystem services and function, including leaf senescence, blooming fruiting, seedling development, and leaf emergence. This leads to alterations in the population dynamics of species that are related at different trophic levels or in mutualistic and competitive relationships. When plants and animals respond differently to environmental changes, plant phenology

can also trigger temporal adjustment in animal phenology, which may lead to phenological mismatching.

Moreover, phenological patterns are often associated with specific reproductive strategies that maximize the reproductive success of a species. A plant's phenology can affect the rate of pollination, herbivory, and other interspecies interactions like the spread of fruit and seeds. The length and frequency of distinct phenophases can vary the availability of resources, which can affect the population dynamics of animal species like herbivores, frugivores, and pollinators. Phenological investigations play a critical role in understanding the ecological adaptations of different plant species and interactions at the community level, as well as from the perspective of tree genetic resources and forestry management. The community's interactions between plants and animals are based on knowledge of the seasonality of plant components. In this present study, we integrated data from observations of the phenology of 42 tree species from dalpurhimmatnagar.

METHODOLOGY:

Between 2021 and 2024, a variety of geographical regions provided the phenological data that were presented in this study. Geographically speaking, the research region is situated at latitude 23.5745N and longitude 73.0309 E. A number of methodical plant phenology investigations using visual observations start to take shape. For all trees whose canopy was visible to the observer, monthly measurements of leaf fall, vegetative growth, fruiting, new foliage, and flowering were made using the oosting method (1958). Since the study's inception, 42 different species of trees on the college campus have received permanent markings, and monthly phenological diagram recordings have been made.

Table 1: List of tree species of Dalpur , Himmatnagar District, Gujarat.

No.	Plant Name	Family	Common Name
1	<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.	Annonaceae	Sitafal
2	<i>Polyalthia longifolia</i> (Sonn.) Thw.	Annonaceae	Asopalav
3	<i>Bombax ceiba</i> L.	Bombacaceae	Shimalo
4	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Correa	Rutaceae	Bili
5	<i>Citrus limon</i> (L.) Burm.f.	Rutaceae	Limbu
6	<i>Citrus medica</i> L.	Rutaceae	Bijoru
7	<i>Limonia acidissima</i> L.	Rutaceae	Kothu
8	<i>Thespesia populnea</i> L. Soland ex. Corr.	Malvaceae	Paraspipado
9	<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i> Roxb.	Simaroubaceae	Arduso
10	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss.	Meliaceae	Limado
11	<i>Ziziphus jujuba</i> Mill.	Rahmnaceae	Boradi
12	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Anacardiaceae	Ambo
13	<i>Acacia nilotica</i> (L.) Delile	Mimosaceae	Bavad
14	<i>Albizia lebbek</i> (L.) Benth.	Mimosaceae	Shirish
15	<i>Bauhinia Purpurea</i> L.	Caesalipiniaceae	Kanchnar
16	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub.	Pepilionaceae	Kesudo
17	<i>Cassia roxburghii</i> DC.	Caesalipiniaceae	Lal Garmado
18	<i>Delonix regia</i> (Hook.) Raf.	Caesalipiniaceae	Gulamahor
19	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.) Pierre	Pepilionaceae	Kanjo
20	<i>Pithecellobium dulce</i> (Roxb) Bth.	Mimosaceae	Goras Amlı
21	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	Caesalipiniaceae	Amlı
22	<i>Terminalia catappa</i> L.	Combrataceae	Deshi Badam
23	<i>Eucalyptus citriodora</i> Hook.	Myrtaceae	Nilgiri
24	<i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	Myrtaceae	Jamfal
25	<i>Callistemon citrinus</i> (Curtis) Skeels	Myrtaceae	Bottal Brush
26	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	Myrtaceae	Jambu
27	<i>Madhuca indica</i> J.F. Gmel.	Sapotaceae	Mahudo
28	<i>Manilkara hexandra</i> (Roxb.) Dubard	Sapotaceae	Rayan
29	<i>Mimusops elengi</i> L.	Sapotaceae	Borsali
30	<i>Salvadora persica</i> L.	Salvadoraceae	Piludi
31	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> (L.) R.Br.	Apocynaceae	Saptparnı
32	<i>Cordia sinensis</i> Lam.	Boraginaceae	Gundi
33	<i>Nyctanthes arbortristis</i> L.	Nyctaginaceae	Parijatak

34	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Ambla
35	<i>Ficus amplissima</i> Sm.	Moraceae	Pipad
36	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> L.	Moraceae	Vad
37	<i>Ficus carica</i> L.	Moraceae	Anjir
38	<i>Ficus racemosa</i> L.	Moraceae	Umaro
39	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L.	Moraceae	Pipado
40	<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i> L.	Arecaceae	Khajoori
41	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Leguminosae	Garmado

Table 2: List of plants according to families

Family	Species %(Relative)
Annonaceae	4.76
Bombacaceae	2.38
Rutaceae	9.52
Malvaceae	2.38
Simaroubaceae	2.38
Meliaceae	2.38
Rahmnaceae	2.38
Anacardiaceae	2.38
Mimosaceae	4.76
Pepilionaceae	4.76
Caesalipiniaceae	9.52
Combrataceae	4.76
Myrtaceae	9.52
Sapotaceae	7.14
Salvadoraceae	2.38
Apocynaceae	2.38
Boraginaceae	4.76
Nyctaginaceae	2.38
Euphorbiaceae	2.38
Moraceae	9.52
Arecaceae	4.76
Leguminosae	2.38

Table 3: Showing the phenological diagram

Plant No.	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
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Abbreviations :

1. Leaf fall; 2. Vegetative growth; 3. Fruiting; 4. Newfoliage; 5. Flowering.

Table 4 : Month wish phonological observation of tree species.

Month	Leaf fall	Vegetative growth	Fruiting	New foliage	Flowering
January	28	7	7	5	16
February	19	6	12	6	19
March	2	5	13	2	30
April	3	7	15	6	26
May	3	11	26	1	16
June	1	13	24	10	14
July	2	17	20	12	9
August	3	28	12	17	8
September	4	33	9	8	6
October	5	31	7	4	5
November	10	30	6	5	7
December	17	22	4	1	10

Figure 2: Showing Month wise phenological observation of tree species

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

The current study, which spans the from year 2021 to 2024, documented 41 plant species from 22 families. The phenological traits seen in the are the growth of vegetation, flowering, new foliage, fruiting, and leaf fall. The phenological diagrams of the selected tree species were tracked and recorded every month of the year. While the inquiry was underway, the tree species that were recognized on region were the Rutaceae, caesalpiniaceae, Mytaceae, Moraceae family, which had 16 species and the highest relative species value, and the 11 families, each of which had one species and the lowest relative species value (Table 2 & Figure 1). Using a phenological diagram, the phenological data of 41 tree species were observed and documented month by month (Table 3)

The current study found that leaf fall was highest from March to April and lowest from February to March. Vegetative growth peaked in September and decreased in March, with August through September having the highest amounts. The newest foliage was observed in March to April. while the least amount was observed in March through May. The highest amounts of fruiting and flowering occurred in the months of August-September and March–April, respectively, whereas the lowest amounts occurred in October and November (Table 4 & Figure 2).

The month of March showed the fewest leaf falls, where as March and April recording showed the highest amounts. the month of March showed the lowest vegetative growth while the month of March showed the highest vegetative growth for plant species. The months of May–June and March–April had the greatest fruiting and flowering, respectively, as seen in the figure and table. January and November witnessed the least number of fruits and flowering, respectively.

CONCLUSION:

The current phenological study's findings indicate that the majority of tree species' phenological phases peaked in terms of leaf fall in January during the cool dry period, fruiting in May at the beginning of the warm dry period (60%) and flowering in March to April during the warm dry period (73% and 76%, respectively). The greatest fruiting occurs in April and July. Vegetative development occurs in most plant species from July to December.

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